

D5.3 Communication and dissemination plan

The INCOVER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 68924

Status box

Title	Draft version of the Website content
Status	Final version
Related Work Package	WP5
Deliverable lead	OIEau
Author(s)	OIEau, AIMEN, ISLE, ICLEI
Internal reviewer(s)	OIEau, AIMEN, ISLE, ICLEI
Contact for queries	incover-contact@oieau.fr
Dissemination level	Public
Due submission date	May 2017 (M12)
Actual submission	31/05/17
Project acronym	INCOVER
Grant agreement number	689242
Funding scheme	H2020-WATER-2014-2015/H2020-WATER-2015-one-stage
Abstract	This document gives an overlook of the communication strategy of INCOVER project implemented by all partners. It details all procedures which have to be followed for communication activities.
Key words	Communication, Dissemination, communication tools, communication channels, social media, website, newsletter, dialogue workshop, innovation workshop

Version	Date	Modified by	Modification details
0	14/03/2017	Camille / OIEau	
1	06/04/2017	Camille / OIEau	Made changes according to what was decided during the webcall.
2	28/04/2017	Camille/OIEau	Made changes according to new inputs and comments from ISLE, AIMEN and ICLEI
3	19/05/2017	Camille / OIEau	Made changes according to latest inputs and comments from ISLE, AIMEN and ICLEI

1	Introduction and background	5
1.1	INCOVER in a nutshell.....	5
1.2	Context of the communication and dissemination plan	5
1.3	Aims of INCOVER communication strategy and key objectives	6
2	Components of INCOVER Communication Strategy	7
2.1	The “WHAT”: messages and content.....	7
2.2	The “WHO”: INCOVER target groups and partners’ role	10
2.2.1	Target groups	10
2.2.2	The role of INCOVER partners.....	15
2.3	The “HOW” – Channels and tools.....	16
2.3.1	Communication and dissemination tools.....	17
2.3.2	Communication and dissemination online channels	20
2.3.3	Communication and dissemination offline channels	24
2.3.4	After the project	26
3	Impact of the communication actions	28
3.1	Monitoring.....	28
3.2	Potential risks and obstacles	28
4	Procedures.....	30
4.1	Updating the website.....	30
4.2	The use of social media	31
4.3	Procedure for Innovation workshops	32
4.4	Procedure for Dialogue workshops.....	33
4.5	Procedure for attending an event and publishing in newspapers, magazines, etc.....	34
4.6	Procedure for the newsletter.....	35
4.7	Form to be filled in after an Innovation Workshop and a Dialogue Workshop	36
4.8	Event’s description form.....	37
5	References	38

Figure 1: Messages along the project lifetime.	7
Figure 2: Source: EU Research and innovation participant portal.....	10
Figure 3 INCOVER target groups with selected examples of how they will be reached through INCOVER events and tools.....	11
Table 1: Specific messages to be communicated.	9
Table 2: Description of target groups.....	12
Table 3: Description of communication tools.	20
Table 4: Summary table: Website tool.....	22
Table 5: Summary table: Social media tools.....	23
Table 6: Summary table: Innovative workshops.....	25
Table 7: Summary table: Dialogue workshops.....	25
Table 8: Potential risks and obstacles in communication activities.....	28
Table 9: Updating the website.....	30
Table 10: The use of social media.....	31
Table 11: Procedure for Innovation Workshops.....	32
Table 12: Procedure for Dialogue Workshops.....	33
Table 13: Communication activities procedure.....	34
Table 14: Procedure for the newsletter.....	35
Table 15: Specific form after IW and DW.....	36

1 Introduction and background

1.1 INCOVER in a nutshell

The aim of INCOVER project is to develop innovative and sustainable added-value technologies for a resource recovery-based treatment of municipal and industrial wastewater, using smart operation monitoring and control methodologies. Three plants treating wastewater from three case studies will be implemented and optimized, to recover energy and added-value products. A Decision Support System (DSS) will be tailored for selecting the most technical, social and cost efficient treatment solutions.

INCOVER solutions aim at reducing at least a 50% overall operation and maintenance cost of wastewater treatment through the use of wastewater as a source of energy and added-value production, to follow UE circular economy strategy. Strategies to facilitate a rapid market uptake of INCOVER innovations will be carried out, in order to close the gap between demonstration and end-users.

1.2 Context of the communication and dissemination plan

As it is stated in the Grant Agreement, communication and dissemination are compulsory.

Communication means *“taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”*¹. Article 38 of the Grant Agreement reminds that *“the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner”*.

Dissemination *“is a process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups [...] in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work”*². Article 29 of the Grant Agreement reminds that *“each beneficiary must – as soon as possible – “disseminate” its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means [...], including in scientific publications”*.

That is why a communication and dissemination strategy needs to be defined (deliverable D5.3). The measures defined in this strategy will permit to catch the eye of potential end-users and ensure the reuse of the results that will be generated.

In addition, communication and dissemination will help and facilitate the exploitation of the results. Exploitation is *“the use of the results during and after the project’s implementation. It can be for commercial purposes but also for improving policies, and for tackling economic and societal problems”*³. INCOVER project has to reach the commercial exploitation and market uptake of the R&I results of the project.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/faqs/faq-933.html>

Communication activities as well as the dissemination and exploitation of the project are carried out in **Work Package 5 – Boosting INCOVER technologies market uptake**. Related tasks of WP5 aim at identifying key stakeholders and technology end-users and preparing the commercial exploitation of INCOVER solutions. The development of this Communication and Dissemination plan (D5.3) is part of Task 5.5, dedicated to communication activities and lead by OIEau.

1.3 Aims of INCOVER communication strategy and key objectives

At the beginning of the project, because results are not yet available, the communication strategy will focus on raising awareness about the project.

Short and medium-term objectives of communication strategy are:

- Make the existence of INCOVER project known as well as its aim, objectives, expected results and future impacts, to the broadest possible audience;
- Announce and promote INCOVER events, partner's participation in public events to promote INCOVER, etc.;
- Announce new publications resulting from INCOVER work (e.g., scientific papers, articles in trade magazines, etc.);
- Support the dissemination objectives;
- Support the exploitation objectives;
- Promote EU research.

Long-term objectives of communication and dissemination strategy are:

- Enhance project exploitation potential (and protect and exploit Intellectual Property);
- Make known INCOVER environmental and social impacts and its benefits for European society;
- Make known INCOVER scientific results (scientific papers, patents, press releases, etc.) and enhance their reuse and impact;
- Catch the interest of each targeted group (scientific community, public authorities, water utilities, industries, etc.);
- Help introducing INCOVER solutions in markets;
- Influence decision-making stakeholders.

2 Components of INCOVER Communication Strategy

The overall communication and dissemination strategy is based on objectives, messages (WHAT), target audience (WHO), means (HOW), planning (WHEN) and monitoring the results.

2.1 The “WHAT”: messages and content

➤ **Key messages**

The key messages of the communication and dissemination strategy have to be defined. They should include arguments and facts to focus on positive achievements and benefits the INCOVER project will bring.

The key messages conveyed will evolve along the project lifetime. INCOVER concept, objectives and expected impacts will be introduced at first. Then, the ongoing activities and project events will be promoted and finally, the outcomes of the project will be communicated and the messages related to the marketing of the products, as shown on the diagram below.

Figure 1: Messages along the project lifetime.

- **High-level message:**

“INCOVER project will transform wastewater from a waste stream into a source of new added-value bio-products, contributing to a circular flow economy, using innovative technologies”.

- **Supporting key messages:**

- Objectives:

“INCOVER main objective is to reduce at least 50% overall operation and maintenance costs of conventional wastewater treatment and alleviate water scarcity”.

“INCOVER will validate innovative recovery technologies at demonstration scale (TRL 7-8) to obtain bio-methane, bio-plastics and organic acids, from wastewater and demonstrate cost-efficient nutrient recovery techniques”.

- INCOVER activities:

“Three added-value plants treating wastewater from municipalities, farms and food and beverage companies will be implemented, assessed and optimized concurrently. They will generate valuable resources from wastewater, such as raw materials, energy and agricultural inputs”.

“INCOVER will develop a Decision Support System tool for providing data and selection criteria for a holistic wastewater management approach”.

“To improve added-value production efficiency, INCOVER solutions will include monitoring via optical sensing and soft-sensors”.

- INCOVER expected results:

“INCOVER project will permit a reduction of energy demand (as least of 50%) of wastewater management”.

“INCOVER project will permit a reduction of GHG emissions up to 80%, using CO₂ sequestration processes”.

“INCOVER project will provide a cost-effective water reuse methodology, in countries facing water scarcity”.

“INCOVER project will increase awareness on the benefits of reused water and bio-products”.

- **Other specific messages:**

Table 1: Specific messages to be communicated.

Overall information	<p><i>Get familiar with the project objectives and activities...</i></p> <p><i>Find out more about the project (video n°1) and about the project results...</i></p>
Case study progress	<p><i>Case-study XX construction started...</i></p> <p><i>Discover case-study XX first results ...</i></p>
Workshops (dialogue workshops)	<p><i>Mark your calendar</i></p> <p><i>BEFORE</i></p> <p><i>Participating in INCOVER dialogue workshop will give you the opportunity to get up to speed with latest waste water treatment technologies with which you can:</i></p> <p><i>(1) produce bio plastics and organic acids;</i></p> <p><i>(2) improve your energy-efficiency, producing upgraded biogas</i></p> <p><i>(3) recover nutrients (N/P) and reclaim water more efficiently</i></p> <p><i>AFTER</i></p> <p><i>X experts from various background such as XXXX, coming from XXX different countries had a chance to learn from INCOVER project partners innovative ways how to... [see above] ... such as...</i></p>
External events	<p><i><EVENT> will feature a presentation about INCOVER project <TOPIC> by <PARTNER>...</i></p> <p><i>INCOVER project has been represented at <EVENT> by <PARTNER> ...</i></p>
Publications, press releases	<p><i><PUBLICATION> features an article about INCOVER project...</i></p> <p><i>INCOVER project recognized by <SCIENTIFIC BODY>...</i></p>

➤ **List of keywords**

Innovation; Circular economy; Resource recovery; Wastewater; Eco-technologies; H2020; Research; Bio-products; Bioenergy; Bio-fertilizer; Water reuse; Agriculture; Municipalities; Industries; Nutrient recovery; CO₂ sequestration processes; Biogas; Biomethane.

➤ **Making EU funding acknowledged**

All partners of the consortium will pay specific attention to acknowledge the EU funding in all communication, publication, dissemination and IPR activities as well as on all equipment, infrastructure and major results funded by the grant, as it is specified in article 38 of the Grant Agreement. They must:

- Display the EU emblem: the EU emblem must be used and not the European Commission's logo (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Source: EU Research and innovation participant portal.

- Include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 689242. The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author’s view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”.

For more information around this topic see: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/acknowledge-funding_en.htm

➤ **Way to convey the message:**

According to the EC’s tips and to the current trends in communication, INCOVER team will try to communicate following the main ideas:

- Scientific messages are not easy to explain that is why effort should be made to be understood, using non-technical language.
- To get people interest, the message should show the impact of the project on the society, and make the message relevant to our everyday lives, so that people understand. This idea is *“Tell story that talk to your audience”*.
- *“Think issue – not project”*: We should wonder *“what issue is the project addressing or contributing to?”*
- *“Be creative”*.

2.2 The “WHO”: INCOVER target groups and partners’ role

2.2.1 Target groups

The more we know the audience and the easier it is to communicate efficiently, to convey the right message in the right way. It is really important to identify targeted groups, in order to adapt the message and to find the best channel to reach them. Each targeted audience should be defined according to its interests or needs. Most of the targeted groups of INCOVER project are potential technology end-users or by-products end-users. However, the project targets also other groups such as policy makers, public in general or the scientific community.

INCOVER project's target groups are identified in Figure 3. Further information describing each target group is provided in Table 2.

Figure 3 INCOVER target groups with selected examples of how they will be reached through INCOVER events and tools.

Table 2: Description of target groups.

Target group	Description	Roles	Means to reach them	Main facilitators
Industrial sector	Industries interested in the developed technologies to treat wastewater, in particular, food and beverage industries . Industries interested in INCOVER by-products use, in particular chemical companies (bio-plastics, bio-coal, organic acids, etc.).	Enhance project's visibility	Dialogue workshops	WP5 members (ICLEI (lead), ISLE, OIEAU) + other partners
		Create market opportunities	Advisory Board	
		Give feedback and recommendations on project development	Europe wide conferences, business-oriented events	
		Foster collaboration	Online tools: website, social media, newsletter, press releases, video Printed communication materials	
Agricultural sector, especially livestock farms	Farms interested in optimizing agricultural wastewater management and waste management Farms interested in the use of bio-fertilizer, irrigation water or biomethane	Enhance project's visibility	Dialogue workshops	WP5 members (ICLEI (lead), ISLE, OIEAU) + other partners
		Create market opportunities	Advisory Board	
		Give feedback and recommendations on project development	Online tools: website, social media, newsletter, press releases, video	
		Foster collaboration	Printed communication materials	
Public and private water utilities	Municipalities interested in optimizing wastewater management (cost and energy consumption reductions, use of innovative recovery techniques, etc.) Municipalities interested in water reuse Wastewater utilities operators	Enhance project's visibility	Innovation workshops	WP5 members (ISLE (lead), ICLEI, OIEAU) + other partners
		Create market opportunities	Dialogue workshops and advisory board (AB)	
		Give feedback and recommendations on project development	Targeted brochures	
		Foster collaboration	Online tools: website, social media, newsletter, press releases, video	

	Wastewater technology providers	Promote INCOVER solutions' benefits for the EU community Support sector development	Printed communication materials (INCOVER general leaflet available in English, Spanish, French and Greek).	
Scientific community	Academia, researchers Scientific community interested in INCOVER's development and results, which can be beneficiary for their own research activities Scientific actors involved in European Projects in the similar areas	Enhance project's visibility Give feedback and recommendations on project development Share experience Foster collaboration Increase the exploitation of INCOVER scientific results	Peer reviewed articles, technical articles Academic activities or events H2020 communication tools (Horizon magazine, Cordis, etc.) Online tools: website, social media, newsletter, press releases, video	All partners
Decision making stakeholders	Local governments Regional authorities European authorities Government bodies Regulators, policy makers	Create financial and institutional support for INCOVER development Create market opportunities	Dialogue workshops Advisory Board Online tools: website, social media, newsletter, press releases, video H2020 communication tools (Horizon magazine, Cordis, etc.) INCOVER partners to participate at/provide input for European wide conferences. Policy briefs	WP5 members (ISLE, ICLEI, OIEAU) + other partners

The general public	Civil citizens Civil society	Enhance project's visibility Promote INCOVER solutions' benefits for the EU community	Online tools: website, social media, newsletter, press releases, video	All partners
---------------------------	---------------------------------	--	--	--------------

It is worth noting that each target group will not be informed in the same way. Wastewater experts can be informed with technical information whereas general public should be informed in a simple and logical way. Individual citizens should be told a simple story, so that we catch their attention. For example, they should be explained what the INCOVER project may change for them, etc.

2.2.2 The role of INCOVER partners

The members of the consortium have a key role to play in the communication actions.

INCOVER consortium is integrated by eight technology providers (FINT, RECIRKU, SIMBIENTE, SSP, AUT, IBET, RENERGIE and BIOTREND), one large European lead-user of wastewater sector (AQUALIA), six research and technical development institutions (AIMEN, AU, UPC, UFZ, UVA and DTI), a water sector dissemination partner (OIEau), a business development and market expert (ISLE) and a global association representing municipal potential end-users of INCOVER solutions (ICLEI). The diversity of the consortium will allow to reach each targeted group (scientific community, wastewater utilities, etc.).

Thus, each partner is expected to take part in communication and dissemination activities, under the overall management of WP5 Leader – ISLE Utilities – and Task 5.5 leader – OIEau. It is worth noting that each partner of the consortium has a few person-months dedicated to WP5, for communication activities, events, etc. They are expected to use their network (research network, collaborators, customers, industrial partners, etc.) and their experience in EC funded projects to:

- Communicating general information on INCOVER project to their respective audience through their company's website in particular
- Providing help in generating traffic to the INCOVER website.
- Providing relevant information to enrich the project website
- Providing relevant information and news to post on the Twitter page
- Raising community interest posting articles on the LinkedIn group page.
- Contributing to the e-newsletter writing (at least 1 newsletter / year)
- Identifying and informing about dissemination opportunities (events, publications, etc.)
- Contributing to scientific research dissemination
- Promoting the project at national and European conferences, workshops, etc.
- Promoting the organisation of the dialogue and innovations workshops
- Using the collaborative internal platform (Freedcamp) to inform on their progress and to provide relevant dissemination activities and opportunities.

Moreover, among each partner, a person has been identified to be the main contact for communication activities and related topics.

It is worth noting that before any communication and dissemination activity, each partner has to follow strict rules of prior notice to all partners, according to EC guidelines and as it is detailed section 4.5.

➤ **Role of the coordinator:**

AIMEN as project coordinator will play a key role in internal and external communication. AIMEN is also involved in IPR issues. So AIMEN will analyse project information contained in public communications of all partners before their publication or/and dissemination, in order to identify possible sensitive information or IPR conflicts (see the whole procedure section 4.5).

➤ **Role of the Advisory Board:**

The main purpose of the Advisory Board is to help overcome (legal, institutional, political, mental etc.) barriers to the application and outscaling of innovative INCOVER technologies, products, and tools and thus facilitate the paradigm shift to perceiving and managing wastewater as a valuable resource instead of as a nuisance to be disposed of as quickly as possible.

In particular, members of the Advisory Board are expected to support INCOVER in:

- Identifying and analysing the most crucial barriers to the uptake of the INCOVER innovations;
- Identifying ways and means to overcome these barriers;
- Taking advantage of their own networks and communication channels to interact with relevant policy-makers to make them aware of such barriers.

Provisional list of invited institutions:

(A) AB members confirmed:

1. Agraçor, S.A. (Portugal).
2. WssTP - EU Water Sanitation and Supply Technology Platform (Europe).
3. COPA-COGECA - EU Association of farmers and agri-cooperatives (Europe).
4. EUREAU (Europe).
5. PATT/ Region of Attica (Greece).
6. CEDEX – Centro de Estudios y Experimentación de Obras Públicas (Spain).

(B) Invited, but final response pending:

7. Aguas do Porto (Portugal).
8. SEGES (Denmark).

2.3 The “HOW” – Channels and tools

First of all, it is worth noting that “**tools**” refers to material supports whereas “**channels**” refer to all media which can convey project information and results to the targeted audiences. Online and

offline channels can be distinguished; indeed, conferences and events are offline ways to disseminate project results to specific audiences.

INCOVER communication and dissemination strategy is based on the use of different communication channels and materials and also on physical interactive events, such as workshops with stakeholders or conferences.

2.3.1 Communication and dissemination tools

➤ **Communication material package**

A first communication material package was due on M6 (November 2017). All the materials contained in this package remain easily available for partners on Freedcamp for INCOVER project. This package includes:

- **Visual identity:**

To ensure a maximum visibility of INCOVER project, a specific logo was designed. It is a key tool to introduce the project to the public and to make people remember the name of the project. The logo must be used in all communication materials. It is available to all partners on **Freedcamp platform** (Files/WP5/Working documents/Logo), in different sizes and in colour and black and white.

Based on the same colour palette (graphic charter), templates for Word documents, project deliverables and for Power Point presentation have been made and are available on **Freedcamp platform** (Files/Admin/Templates).

- **Leaflet and poster:**

A leaflet and a poster have already been produced at M6 to introduce the project, the topic, its objectives and activities. They are **available on Freedcamp** for partners and are also downloadable on the project website, which should allow their large spreading through the internet. They can also be printed to be handed out at each event.

The leaflet is available in English, French, Spanish and Greek.

- **Standard PowerPoint presentation:**

A PowerPoint presentation has been prepared and is **available on Freedcamp** to all partners, so that they can use it when they attend an event. This document emphasises INCOVER's objectives, activities (case-studies), benefits, etc.

- **Roll-up banner (85 x 200):**

By the end of June 2017 (M13), a generic roll-up banner with fundamental information around INCOVER project will be designed. This promotional and advertising material can be used for exhibitions, conferences, workshops, etc. The digital version will be **available on Freedcamp**.

- **Videos**

Videos are an effective and eye-catching way to communicate. Using infographics, they can convey a complex message easily and effectively to the general public. Short videos are becoming a tool increasingly used and fit with the trend of storytelling. That is why a short video trailer will be produced (animated video) to promote and explain clearly the project's concept and objectives. Then, filmed parts could be added, showcasing the INCOVER solutions, case-studies or interviews. The video will be published on the project website and on YouTube, shared on social networks, used during events and promoted through external channels. Video will be provided between M18-M24.

OIEau will be in charge of the video and its content and story will be validated by WP5 partners. According to D7.3, an "*Informed consent paper*" will be presented and signed by persons who may appear/be recorded on the short videos.

- **Press releases with no result dissemination**

Each partner is committed to produce press releases and articles for social media. Their publication must follow the procedure detailed section 4.5. Press-releases permit to raise awareness about the project activities, benefits and outputs. They are an efficient communication way to make the existence of the project known and to inform about relevant milestones, project events, etc. They are intended for all target audiences (general public, policy makers, etc.) and do not require specific knowledge to be understood.

Each time there is a press release, it will be widely disseminated through the project website and social media.

- **Target publications and scientific magazines**

Partners are also committed to submit papers to professional newspapers and for peer-reviewed publication in international journals. These papers should be, as far as possible, in open access journals or specialized magazines. They permit project results dissemination and their reuse, targeting specifically wastewater experts, technology providers and the scientific community.

- **Project public deliverables**

All public project deliverables will be available and downloadable on the project website. This will permit to keep the public informed on the project's progress and to increase the knowledge on the project.

➤ **E-newsletter**

In order to keep all stakeholders informed on project's developments, latest activities and events, a newsletter will be issued, at least annually. It will be sent to each person who has subscribed to the newsletter on the project website. It will also be sent to the stakeholders registered in the database hold by ISLE. Each partner will also disseminate the newsletter through its own network. Then, each newsletter edition will be uploaded on the website, for the general public to access. The procedure to write and send the newsletter is detailed section 4.6.

➤ **Other specific tools**

Other specific material tools will be developed to suit partners' needs when they attend an event, or to suit the targeted audience of each workshop.

For example, for the **Innovation Workshops**, Isle will use a short brochure tailored to wastewater management experts to inform them on the INCOVER project - specifically the technologies and bio-products, and invite them to participate (either via the Innovation Workshops, or joining the mailing list for the newsletters etc.).

Moreover, in T5.7, ICLEI ES will produce an electronic template for a leaflet targeting the general public and explaining why water consumption in food production needs to be reduced and why WW treated with latest technologies does not imply any risks in hygiene and health. Doing so, Local Governments will have a flexible basis on which they can build the production of their own tailored materials.

Communication tools are summarized in Table 4. Each tool disseminating project results should follow the procedure described section 4.5.

Table 3: Description of communication tools.

Tool	Role	Objectives	Targeted audiences	When, by when
Communication material package	To raise awareness about INCOVER project	Produce relevant communication tools, tailored to each target group.	All audiences	M2 and updates later
Video	To introduce clearly and easily INCOVER concepts	> 300 views every 6 months.	All audiences	M18 – M24
Newsletter	To keep stakeholders informed on INCOVER progress	Size of the dissemination list by M36 > 1,500	All audiences	At least M12, M24 and M36
Press releases with no result dissemination	To raise awareness about INCOVER project	Number of press releases per year: 2 per year.	All audiences	From M1 to M36
Scientific articles, peer-reviewed publications	To increase results dissemination and reuse	Number of peer-reviewed publications: between 12 – 20 at the end of the project	Scientific community, public and private water utilities	From M12 to M36
Public deliverables	To keep stakeholders informed on INCOVER progress	According to the GA.	All audiences	Each time a public deliverable is done

2.3.2 Communication and dissemination online channels

➤ **Project website:**

Description:

A specific website for INCOVER project has been created by OIEau (T5.5), at the following addresses:

- www.incover-project.eu
- www.incover.org

The project website is a main pathway for spreading information about INCOVER project. It will be used to diffuse project information as widely as possible. It is the primary information source for the target audiences. Its address will feature in all project's communication materials (flyer, poster, etc.).

The project website is used for both communication and dissemination activities. As soon as the first scientific results from the case-studies are available, they will be published on the website.

The website provides:

- Updated information on the project activities, events, internal events, latest news (publications, etc.).
- Overall information on the project: concept, objectives, partners, activities (case-studies), benefits, impacts and applications.
- Technical information and description of the technologies developed and the bio-products obtained
- Possibilities for downloading deliverables, press releases, communication materials, etc.
- Possibilities for contacting INCOVER staff and technology providers, etc.

The website benefits from an eye-catching design and a responsive design, which should allow to reach a large audience and to permit easier navigation (from smartphones, tablets, etc.)

Role:

The purpose of the website is to promote the project and its final results by providing targeted information to various audiences.

Browsing through the website, the scientific community will be provided new knowledge and scientific results, technical descriptions of technologies, scientific publications, etc. The water utilities experts will be provided the right skills, the understanding of the technologies and bio products, case studies information, etc. Meanwhile, the decision-making stakeholders and public bodies will be given overall information, awareness on the project's objectives, results, benefits and applicability. Moreover, awareness will be raised among individual citizens, so that they understand the potential project impacts on their everyday lives, etc.

The specific goals of the website are:

- To raise awareness about the project (results, benefits, use, etc.) among each target audience;
- To enhance understanding and facilitate the adoption of project results;
- To get people interest in the project, subscribing to the newsletter;
- To promote events (Innovation workshops, Dialogues workshops, etc.).

Maintenance:

OIEau is in charge of the maintenance and the update of the website. Each partner is committed to provide relevant information for the website (see procedure section 4.1.).

The website uses Google analytics systems to monitor the traffic (number of visitors, provenance, etc.).

To improve the management of INCOVER website (to count visitors, to see where visitors are going on the website, etc.), the website uses *Google Analytics system*. Explanation on the use of the system are provided in the legal notice.

Current situation:

Between: 1/02/2017 –29/05/2017:

Number of sessions: 819

Number of visitors: 536

Average duration visit: 03:34

Percentage of new visitors: 62.03%

Summary table:

Table 4: Summary table: Website tool

Channel	Role	Objectives	Targeted audiences
Website	To promote the project and its final results by providing targeted information to various audiences.	Number of visitors by M24: 900 Number of visitors by M36: 1500	All audiences

➤ **Social media accounts**

The use of social media will help to make the existence of INCOVER project known and to relay information as widely as possible in Europe, to all audiences. They can be used to convey technical or non-technical information, to advertise events, to initiate discussions and comments, to share and advertise interesting scientific news to the community and to get people interest.

- **Twitter page**

The INCOVER twitter page has been launched at M6 (@INCOVERproject). The project website allows the visualization of the last tweet published. Getting journalists as followers, as well as European Commission accounts, could be really useful to have INCOVER information relayed - they can act as multipliers.

Useful tips/recommendations for the use of Twitter: Write concise message, focus on one topic per message, link the message to a web page if needed, send messages regularly and frequently, use “we” and “our”.

A reminder:

Tweet: message posted on Twitter (<140 characters)

Retweet (RT): send someone else’s tweet to your followers

Mention @: They refer to a tweet that includes a reference to a twitter user

Hashtag #: They refer to a topic. For example: #Circular economy; #H2020, #ResearchImpactEU; #wastewater; #reuse; #reduce; #water

Maintenance: OIEau is in charge of the activity on the Twitter page, but all partners are involved in this activity and have log-on details, so that they can tweet whenever they want. Moreover, from their own twitter account they can strengthen the visibility of INCOVER page. An e-mail will be sent by ISLE monthly to remind them to use INCOVER twitter page.

Current situation: Currently (29/05/2017) INCOVER Twitter page has 91 followers and 77 tweets.

Thanks to *Twitter Analytics system*, the number of view of the profile can be monitored, as well as the number of view of each tweet, etc.

- **LinkedIn Group**

INCOVER project account has been launched in February 2017. Partners of the project have been invited to join the group, to invite their network and to initiate discussions. The LinkedIn group can serve as a platform for formal discussions, interaction, and communication of the project outputs. It can reach people interested in water issues and can also reach wastewater experts. The LinkedIn group can be an ideal location to engage with stakeholders.

Maintenance: OIEau is administrator and other members are moderators. All members can invite new persons to join the group.

Current situation: Currently (29/05/17) the LinkedIn group has 54 members and 14 short posts.

- **YouTube account**

A channel will be created to disseminate the project videos.

Table 5: Summary table: Social media tools.

Channel	Role	Objectives	Targeted audiences
Twitter	To raise awareness about INCOVER project and to keep stakeholders informed on INCOVER progress	Number of followers by M18: >300?	All audiences
LinkedIn group	To raise awareness about INCOVER project and to engage with stakeholders	Size of LinkedIn group by M18: >100 members	All audiences, particularly persons involved in the water sector

➤ Contact databases

T5.1 consisting in identifying and quantifying market opportunities and key stakeholders will develop a stakeholder database, throughout the duration of the project. The database will be regularly updated with new contacts made at conferences, workshops, etc., especially technology end-users and people from municipal, industrial and agricultural sectors. This database will allow easier targeted communication, and will be used to send the newsletter, invitations to events, etc.

Maintenance and current situation: Contact databases have already been created and they are updated whenever a new stakeholder is identified. All partners can suggest new contacts to add to the databases

Current situation: At M10 around 200 contacts have been identified and added to the databases

➤ External channels

External websites will disseminate project activities and results for awareness purposes, such as:

- **Partners' website:** Because communication starts among the consortium and through each partner's network, partners' are expected to mention INCOVER project on their websites and to relay information.
- **Other EU-related projects' websites:** Other EU-projects dealing with the same topics can communicate about INCOVER project on their websites (providing the link of INCOVER website). In the same way, the link to their website will appear on INCOVER website (backlinks).
- **European Commission's websites:** The European Commission can help spread information on the project and acts as a multiplier. Project officer must be kept informed by the coordinator about interesting topics, news and events. Publications can occur in Horizon magazine, CORDIS, etc.
- **Websites of specialized magazines,** or technical magazines, such as RETEMA in Spain.
- **Open access repositories** such as OpenAire and Zenodo, where final results will be published.

➤ Freedcamp platform for internal communication

To share information through the consortium and to facilitate internal communication, the online private Freedcamp platform is used. It allows to share documents, to initiate discussions, etc. among each person involved in the project.

It is important to use all these channels to ensure a maximum impact of INCOVER project and to reach each target audience. The efficient communication and dissemination depends on the combination of the use of all these channels.

2.3.3 Communication and dissemination offline channels

➤ Project events

Various project events will be held to identify and engage with technology and by-products end-users. They will help spreading the project outputs to the respective target audiences, to facilitate

feedback from respective stakeholders, etc. Tables 7 and 8 describe the objectives of these project events.

- **Innovative workshops:**

Table 6: Summary table: Innovative workshops.

Role/objective of the event	Targeted audiences	Quantified objectives	Where/when	Output
Put the INCOVER technology developers in direct contact with technology end-users	Public and private water utilities	Number of participants expected: 10-15 Number of events: 1 Innovation Workshop Training and 3 Innovation Workshops	Spain and/or Germany during the INCOVER technical meetings	Feedback from all technology end-users

- **Dialogue workshops:**

Table 7: Summary table: Dialogue workshops.

Role/objective of the event	Targeted audiences	Quantified objectives	Where/when	Output
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To familiarise end-users with the technological concept and expected benefits of the INCOVER technology; • To get an expert opinion from end-users with regard to the requirements which the new INCOVER technology would have to comply with (including considerations regarding public procurement) in order to increase its fitness for purpose and future success on the market; • To receive recommendations from end-users on how to accelerate up-take and acceptance of the new technology in cities and also the products obtained by INCOVER solutions. 	Agricultural sector	Number of participants expected:	WS 1: Leipzig, Germany, June 2017	One brief report per workshop on key points from discussion
	Industrial sector	WS 1 & 2: 15 to 20 participants each	WS 2: Barcelona, Spain, March 2018	
	Public and private waste water utilities	WS 3: 40 to 50 participants	WS 3: Andalusia, Spain, May 2019	
	Private sector/SMEs	Number of events: 3		
	Consultants			

➤ External events

All partners will be actively participating in external events such as European wide conference and business-oriented events. Each external event is an opportunity to raise awareness about INCOVER project, to wider disseminate the project activities and outputs to stakeholders and the public at large.

At M12, INCOVER project has already been introduced at:

- The Watex Exhibition in Teheran, in September 2016, by SolarSpring.
- The AlgaEurope Congress, in December 2016, by AQUALIA, UVA and IBET
- The Bioeconomy Matchmaking “from the molecule to the market”, in March 2017, by UFZ.
- The Italian Forum on Microalgal Technologies in Italy, in May 2017, by UPC.

A conference database of external events where INCOVER could be introduced is maintained by ISLE on Freedcamp. ISLE will send an email to the consortium as a reminder that this list of events is in the Freedcamp monthly.

“Maintenance” of the list: The list on Freedcamp will be regularly updated on a monthly basis by ISLE. Members will be asked to send a list of other events of interest that might not be included in the list. They have to pay attention to events where INCOVER team could contribute.

Procedure:

Once partners have identified interesting meetings they would attend, they must provide details on their planned participation and follow the procedure detailed section 4.5.

After each external event they contributed to, they have to send news and photos to OIEau, to update the project website and social media accounts.

Objectives: Number of events to be attended by INCOVER project partners: average 8/year

2.3.4 After the project

ISLE will support INCOVER technologies to accelerate market uptake via:

1. Facilitation of relationships/partnerships
2. Participation at the ISLE Technology Approval Group (this is ISLE’s global innovation platform where INCOVER solutions can present and engage directly with the world’s leading water utilities)
3. Targeted market studies for the INCOVER technologies
4. Trials or demo projects with end users following the end of the project.

All Partners: After the end of the project, scientific papers will surely be produced and presentation at conferences as well.

Other European projects related to wastewater treatment and circular economy will also probably follow and be a natural continuation of INCOVER project. INCOVER case-studies facilities and infrastructures could be updated or modified to use them in other DEMO projects.

3 Impact of the communication actions

3.1 Monitoring

According to what has been introduced previously, most of the communication and dissemination objectives have been quantified so that we can monitor the impact of the communication strategy and adjust objectives if needed.

For example, the website impact will be monitored thanks to Google Analytics system, which enables counting the number of visitors, seeing their provenance, etc. In the same way, Twitter analytics allows to monitor the traffic on INCOVER Twitter profile.

Moreover, OIEau will keep track of progress of communication activities (in a dissemination log, updated monthly), and the Communication and Dissemination plan will be updated at least annually.

3.2 Potential risks and obstacles

This section aims at identifying the potential difficulties we can meet in communication activities and identifying solutions to ensure successful communication activities. Table 8.

Table 8: Potential risks and obstacles in communication activities.

Potential risks/obstacles	Ways of minimizing risks, solutions
No scientific results during the first year of the project could induce a lack of communication	Even if scientific results are not available during the first months of the project, each partner should share their progress, case study implementation, etc. and participate actively in all communication activities (sending photos, press release, etc.)
Poor internal communication	Tools such as emails, Freedcamp platform, LinkedIn group, etc. should be used by each partner. Mechanisms are needed so people need to know who to contact, and avoid duplication of work, etc. Section 4 of this document aims at clarifying procedures. Unnecessary emails should be avoided.
Lack of activity on Twitter page	To make it works, a twitter page must be updated regularly. To increase activity, each partner will have access to the page and the possibility to Tweet.

Potential risks/obstacles	Ways of minimizing risks, solutions
Difficulties in engaging with the audience	Although awareness around INCOVER project may be successful, real engagement with the target group may be difficult. Innovation and dialogue workshops will minimize this risk. The combination of the different dissemination and communication routes are there in place to minimize the risks.

4 Procedures

The following section provides a detailed description for each task, comprising the necessary information for the implementation of the communication strategy and procedures. Each of the below-mentioned tasks are further described in order to detail the procedures for their implementation.

4.1 Updating the website

Table 9: Updating the website.

Updating the website	
WHO	<p>OIEau is the main responsible for the website management. OIEau makes changes and functionalities adjustments.</p> <p>All partners are involved in providing new content for the website and are requested to send information to update the website.</p> <p>If the updates are long texts in English, ISLE may be in charge of proofreading.</p>
WHEN	<p>The website can be easily updated when there is something new. Updates can be about project meetings and events, upcoming related events, available new visual material, work progress information (construction of the case study, new results, promotion of event, etc.).</p>
HOW	<p>Partners have to send their updates to OIEau. If all information needed are provided, OIEau will update the website shortly after receiving the information.</p>
WHAT	<p>When sending information, partners have to provide the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The page of the website they want to be updated with their content and the section - Title of the article if needed, link to other websites if necessary, etc. - Photos must be accompanied by a caption and copyrights - All other details which could facilitate the update <p>Attention: if the information to be published may contain sensitive information, partners have to follow the procedure detail section 4.5.</p>

4.2 The use of social media

Table 10: The use of social media.

Use of social media (Twitter and LinkedIn)	
WHO	<p><u>Twitter page</u>: All partners are involved in updating the Twitter page, they have log-on details.</p> <p><u>LinkedIn group</u>: OIEau is administrator of the group and each partner can (and must) join the group.</p> <p>In case of problem with one of these social media, OIEau must be contacted.</p>
WHEN	These social media can be used whenever necessary. They are especially useful for instant communication.
HOW	<p><u>Twitter page</u>: Each member has access to the Twitter page and can easily make tweets, retweets, etc.</p> <p><u>LinkedIn group</u>: Each member can join the group and has the possibility to publish articles, to react, and to invite other persons to join the group.</p>
WHAT	<p>Tweets or posts can be made on Twitter and on the LinkedIn group:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to promote project activities - to establish contact with other key stakeholders - to share information related to the theme of INCOVER project - to keep INCOVER project “alive” and proactive in promotion. <p>Tweets should include relevant Hashtags (#) to streamline relevant topics (#wastewater #circulareconomy #bioproducts #bioenergy #ResearchImpactEU, etc.). They can also include @ to mention other users.</p> <p>The LinkedIn group should be a place for professionals in the same industry or with similar interests to share content, find answers, make business contacts, and establish themselves as industry experts.</p> <p><u>Attention</u>: if the information to be published may contain sensitive information, partners have to follow the procedure detailed section 4.5.</p>

4.3 Procedure for Innovation workshops

Table 11: Procedure for Innovation Workshops.

Procedure for Innovation workshops (before and after)	
WHO	<p><u>Main responsible:</u> ISLE</p> <p><u>Participants:</u> European public and private water utilities; INCOVER technology partners</p> <p><u>Support required:</u> Where required, ISLE will contact INCOVER partners to facilitate introductions to the water utilities we are unable to engage with.</p>
WHEN	<p>To directly connect INCOVER technology partners with municipalities (technology end-users), the Innovation Workshops are scheduled as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training Session with INCOVER consortium, June 2017 - Leipzig - Innovation Workshop 1 - November 2017 - Spain (tbc) - Innovation Workshop 2 - May 2018 - Spain / Germany - Innovation Workshop 3 - May 2019, Spain / Germany
HOW	<p><u>Communication activities before the Innovation Workshop:</u> ISLE will invite all European public and private water utilities to participate in the Innovation Workshops.</p> <p><u>Communication activities after the Innovation Workshops:</u> ISLE will circulate to the consortium the summary of minutes and specific feedback from participating European public and private water utilities.</p> <p><u>Dissemination of Innovation Workshop before, during and after event:</u> In addition to INCOVER's communication channels, ISLE will promote the event through our website, LinkedIn and Twitter account.</p> <p>To facilitate the communication after the event, ISLE will fill in the special descriptive form (see section 4.7) and send it to OIEau.</p>
WHAT	<p>Structure of workshops:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Presentations ○ Q&A Session ○ Closed discussion with end-users stakeholders (European private and public water utilities) ○ Collation and circulation of feedback to INCOVER partner after each event

4.4 Procedure for Dialogue workshops

Table 12: Procedure for Dialogue Workshops.

Procedure for Dialogue workshops (before and after)	
WHO	<p><u>Main responsible:</u> ICLEI</p> <p><u>Participants:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholders who are particularly relevant for the INCOVER case study presented in the programme; Selected project partners for inputs to programme, again depending on case study in focus at particular workshop. <p>Other interested project partners.</p>
WHEN	<p>WS 1: Leipzig, Germany, June 2017 WS 2: Barcelona, Spain, March 2018 WS 3: Andalucía, Spain, May 2019</p>
HOW	<p>Each Dialogue Workshop will typically consist of a joint session and separate parallel sessions for each end-user group.</p> <p>Each Dialogue Workshop will also include a technical visit, showing the INCOVER technologies under development.</p> <p>The audience for the Dialogue Workshops will mainly be composed by people/ institutions that will be proposed by the partners responsible for the relevant case study in each case. However, other partners will also be asked for suggestions. The Dialogue Workshops will also be made known via partners' websites, newsbits and similar communication channels. Other interested people can thus also express their interest and will be invited (or not invited) after coordination with the partner in charge for the case study.</p>
WHAT	<p><u>Communication activities before the Dialogue Workshop:</u> All project partners will be requested to promote workshops through their professional circles and using their own media channels. For this, ICLEI will provide them with a brief description of the workshop and the agenda.</p> <p><u>Communication activities after the Dialogue Workshops:</u> All partners will be requested to support the dissemination of a summary of key conclusions.</p> <p>To facilitate the communication after the event, ICLEI will fill in the special descriptive form (see section 4.7) and send it to OIEau.</p>

4.5 Procedure for attending an event and publishing in newspapers, magazines, etc.

Table 13: Communication activities procedure.

Attending an event and/or publishing	
WHO	All partners, Innovation Board and AIMEN.
WHEN	<p>If the piece of work to be disseminated includes results, partner have to send it to Coordinator (AIMEN) 45 calendar days before the publication.</p> <p>If the piece of work to be disseminated does not include results, partners have to send it to the coordinator (AIMEN) 10 calendar days before the Event/publication.</p>
HOW	<pre> graph TD A[Partner X emails AIMEN and details the piece of work to be disseminated] --> B{Is IB approval necessary?} B -- YES --> C[AIMEN emails members of the IB to have their objections if they have] C --> D[If no objections are made, AIMEN emails all IB members, partner X and OIEau to communicate the approval of the dissemination] B -- NO --> E[AIMEN emails the partner X (and copies OIEau) to communicate the approval of the dissemination] D --> F[Partner X sends information to OIEau on its dissemination activity (along with event's description form, publication, photos, press releases, etc.)] E --> F F --> G[OIEau adds news on the project website, the Twitter page and the LinkedIn group.] </pre> <p>If AIMEN identifies vulnerable IPR information, AIMEN will provide the opportunity to Innovation Board members to make objections before 30 calendar days. The maximum publication delay will be 90 calendar days.</p> <p><u>Note:</u> After an event, each partner is expected to send information on its participation in the event, photos, etc. to OIEau, so that news can be uploaded on the website.</p>

4.6 Procedure for the newsletter

Table 14: Procedure for the newsletter

Procedure for writing and sending the newsletter	
WHO	<p><u>Main responsible:</u> OIEau and WP5 members</p> <p><u>Participants:</u> All partners are involved in the creation of the newsletter</p> <p><u>Audience:</u> Members who have subscribed on the website, followers on Twitter, members of LinkedIn Group, members of the stakeholder database and partners' network.</p>
WHEN	<p>At least one newsletter will be published per year.</p> <p>Partners will have at least 2 weeks to provide their content to OIEau.</p>
HOW	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) OIEau will send to all partners a document to be filled in, with the different sections of the newsletter. 2) Once the content is received, OIEau will produce the newsletter. 3) OIEau will send the newsletter to the targeted audience and to partners (in HTML format) 4) All partners are expected to send the newsletter to their network <u>within the 3 days following the first release.</u> 5) All partners will have to tell OIEau which system they use to send the newsletter and give an estimated number of the persons reached, to monitor the audience. 6) OIEau will also upload each newsletter edition on the website, for the general public to access.
WHAT	<p>The different sections covered by the newsletter could be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project coordinator's note - INCOVER at a glance - News from the field (cases-study) - Recent events - Upcoming events - Etc. <p>The structure of the newsletter may change during the project.</p>

4.7 Form to be filled in after an Innovation Workshop and a Dialogue Workshop

This form has to be filled in by ISLE/ICLEI after an Innovation Workshop/Dialogue Workshop and has to be sent to OIEau, within the week following the event. The information it contains needs to be collected in order to post news on the project website, Twitter page or to prepare articles for the next newsletter.

Table 15: Specific form after IW and DW.

Description of the Innovation workshops/Dialogue Workshop													
Date													
Location													
Participants	Number: List:												
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Name</th> <th>Organisation/company</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Name	Organisation/company										
	Name	Organisation/company											
Key topics covered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - XXXXXXXXXXXXX - XXXXXXXXXXXXX 												
Brief description													
Photos													
	Caption: XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX Source: XXXXXXXX <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> Caption: XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX Source: XXXXXXXX												

4.8 Event's description form

This form has to be filled in by ALL partners before they attend an event. Then, they have to send it to OIEau, so that OIEau publish news on the website/twitter page/LinkedIn group and promote the event.

You are going to attend a public event and promote INCOVER project, please, fill in this short form so we can update INCOVER website and social media pages, and send it to WP5 members (AIMEN, ISLE, and OIEau).

Event's title:		
Start date:	End date:	Location:
Where can we find information on this event (e.g., website)?		
Description of your participation (platform presentation, poster, networking, etc.):		
Name of Presenter(s) with Affiliation(s):		
Title and abstract of your presentation(s)? :		
<p>Please, once it is validated by AIMEN, upload your presentation on Freedcamp, in the "Events" folder, following the naming convention : NAME OF THE EVENT_LOCATION_DD/MM/YY</p>		

5 References

European Commission. **Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants**. September 2014, 14p.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

Webinar: <http://www.streamdis.eu/commsworkout2/>

<http://ttopstart-academy.com/resources/communication-vs-dissemination/>